

Nina Thornhill – A Great Mentor

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Abstract: Professor Choudhury collaborated closely with Nina while pursuing his PhD at the University of Alberta, Canada with Prof. Sirish Shah between 2000 and 2002. Their work on valve stiction detection and modeling has found great attention amongst academic researchers and industrial practitioners.

Keywords: University of Alberta, valve stiction, modeling, control loop performance diagnosis.

I met Prof Nina Thornhill at the University of Alberta, Canada, in Summer 2000 when I just started the literature review of my PhD research project in the broad area of Control Loop Performance, specifically on Control Valve Stiction. During that time, Nina came to the University of Alberta as visiting Professor for one year. She worked with Prof Sirish Shah's group.

Prof Sirish Shah was my PhD supervisor. Since Nina was also working closely in the broad area of control loop performance, my supervisor tagged me with Nina. So, I started working with her. I also spent one and half month in her lab in University College London, UK in Spring 2002.

Though she was not my official co-supervisor, she was more than that. She was an amazing lady. I have many sweet memories with her. I learnt innumerable things from her. I still remember when she corrected my draft papers, she used to provide me many comments to improve the manuscript. Some of them are still vivid in my mind - such as "Readers cannot read your mind", "Write everything clearly", "It is better to get harsh comments from me instead of from strangers (reviewers)". She also used to provide comments on how to arrange the subject matters in a logical cohesion manner and make it more readable. I even learnt how to do efficient coding in Matlab from her.

All these have helped me tremendously to grow in those difficult days of my graduate student life. Eventually, we together have written many conference papers, five journal papers, one book, one book chapter and an international patent. Most of our papers have already crossed two hundred citations; one of them is even more – more than 300 citations. This was an excellent teamwork with a high impact. It serves as a glaring example of successful collaboration. Really, "two plus two is more than four" I believe it.

I feel myself very fortunate to work with two great professors, Nina and Sirish. They are my great mentors. I am grateful to them for their invaluable contributions in my life. May Almighty provide them with a long peaceful healthy life and guide them to the right path so that they are successful both in this life and in the life hereafter.

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